

A study of the fluorescence system of terbium-enoxacin and its applications

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Terbium fluorescence sensitized by enoxacin via the formation of an organic chelate, was used for the sensitive determination of terbium. The fluorescence intensity was a linear function of the concentration in the range $5.0 \times 10^{-8} \sim 8.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³ and the detection limit was 1.0×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³ for Tb-enoxacin(EFLX)-CTMAB system. The system was applied to the determination of terbium in the rare earth samples with satisfactory results.

The use of β -diketones as chelating agents, have been used in the spectrofluorimetric determination of trace amounts rare earth ions¹. Recently, application of biological agents, such as quinolone group has drawn more attention. Terbium(III) forms highly fluorescent complex with norfloxacin² and nalidixic acid³. The presence of surfactant can enhance the fluorescence intensity. Previous literature have reported some methods for the determination of norfloxacin and nalidixic acid.

But the fluorescence system of europium with enoxacin (EFLX) has not been reported. Enoxacin[1-ethyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-naphthyridine carboxylic acid] is the third representative of antibacterial medicine, namely, quinolone group. It is used as antibacterial medicine in the treatments of urinary-tract infections, gonorrhoea and bacterial enteritis⁴. EFLX has active grouping in the form of COOH and C=O capable of chelate formation with metal ions.

In this paper, the fluorescent characteristics of the europium complex with EFLX in the presence of CTMAB are reported. The use of the Tb-EFLX-CTMAB system for the spectrofluorimetric determination of europium is described with satisfactory results.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the uncorrected excitation and emission spectra of Tb, EFLX, Tb-EFLX and Tb-EFLX-CTMAB systems at pH 7.0. The emission peaks at 487, 542, 581

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectra (Tb-EFLX-CTMAB) : (a) excitation spectra and (b) emission spectra : (1) Tb, (2) EFLX, (3) Tb-EFLX, (4) Tb-EFLX-CTMAB; [Tb] = 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, [EFLX] = 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [CTMAB] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, 2.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ HMTA-HCl (pH = 7.0).

and 616 nm are attributed to the $^5D_4 \rightarrow ^7D_n$ ($n = 6, 5, 4, 3$) transition of terbium. It can be seen that the emission line at 542 nm is the most intense. Hence, this wavelength was used in further experiments. By adding suitable amount of CTMAB to Tb-EFLX system, the fluorescence can be enhanced.

Effect of pH and species of buffers solutions : The fluorescence intensity of a 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ terbium solution was measured over the pH range 4.0–10.0 by using hexamine-hydrochloric acid buffer solution and adjusting the pH with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide solution. The terbium fluorescence intensity was obtained at pH 7.0.

The fluorescence intensity of Tb-EFLX-CTMAB system was measured at pH 7.0 with same species of the buffer solution. The results are shown in Table 1. The experiments show that the hexamine-hydrochloric is best, and the optimum amounts is 2.0 ml.

The effects of different surfactants on fluorescence in-

Table 1. Effect of buffers

Buffers	Tris-HCl	HMTA-HCl	NH ₄ Ac-HAc	NH ₃ -NH ₄ Cl	H ₃ BO ₄ -HCl
Relative fluorescence	39	45	23	31	39
	HMTA : NH ₃ -NH ₄ Cl		1 : 1	1 : 2	1 : 3
	Relative fluorescence		34.5	26.5	17
					3 : 1
					27.5

Table 2. Determination of Tb^{III} in standard samples of lanthanide oxides*

Tb ^{III} in samples (μg)	Tb ^{III} Found (μg)	Mean±RSD
20.0	20.2, 20.2, 20.4, 20.3, 20.1, 20.5, 25.1, 25.0, 25.5,	20.2±0.1
25.0	24.8, 24.9, 25.2,	25.1±0.3

*Synthetic mixture contained : Y (310), La (190), Ce (440), Pr (56) Nd (240), Sm (105), Eu (11), Gd (63), Tb (10), Dy (43), Ho (12), Er (24) Tm (21), Yb (26), Lu (7) and Tb μg per 100 ml of solution.

tensity at fixed concentration of europium (1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³) were studied, and a 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ CTMAB solution was selected as the optimum.

The effect of the EFLX concentration of fluorescence intensity at fixed concentration of europium 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ was studied. A maximum and constant fluorescence intensity was obtained at $5.0 \times 10^{-6} \sim 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³ of EFLX. Hence, 1.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ of EFLX solution was used in further experiments.

The effect of different solvents on fluorescence intensity at fixed concentration of terbium (1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³) was studied. Relative fluorescence in different solvents were as follows : water, 18; methanol, 25; ethanol, 30; dimethylformamide, 24. Hence water was used as solvent.

Stability of the complex was studied. The effect of the time for the relative fluorescence intensity showed that fluorescence intensity reached the maximum value within 5 min, and remained stable more than 4 h.

Under the optimum conditions, the fluorescence intensity was a linear function of terbium in the range of $5.0 \times 10^{-8} \sim 8.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mol dm⁻³, the detection limit (signal-to-noise ratio = 3) being 1.0×10^{-9} mol dm⁻³.

The effect of foreign ions on the fluorescence intensity of the Tb-EFLX-CTMAB system was studied for 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ terbium. The tolerance allowed in the variation of the fluorescence intensity was $\pm 10\%$. The tolerance limits for other trivalent lanthanide ions were as follows : La^{III}, 8; Ce^{III}, Fe^{III} (5); Gd^{III}, 2.5; Sc^{III}, 2.0; Nd^{III}, 1.5;

Eu^{III}, Dy^{III}, Ho^{III}, Er^{III}, Al^{III}, 1.0; Pr^{III}, Sm^{III}, Tm^{III}, Y^{III}, Ln^{III}, 0.5.

The method was applied to the determination of trace amount of terbium in synthetic rare earth oxides. The results (Table 2) show that the proposed method is suitable for the determination of trace amounts of terbium.

Experimental

Fluorescence intensity was measured on an Hitachi-850 spectrophotometer using 1.0 cm quartz cells; excitation and emission slits were both 10 nm. The pH was measured with a PHS-2 pH meter.

A.R. grade chemicals were used. Solutions were prepared in distilled water.

The lanthanide oxides were obtained from Baotou of China in purity of at least 99.9% and their stock solutions were prepared in HCl. Working solutions were obtained by further appropriate dilution with water.

A 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ solution of enoxacin was prepared in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution and diluted to 250 ml with water.

The buffer solution used was 1.0 mol dm⁻³ hexamine adjusted to pH 7.0 with HCl.

General procedure : To each of a series of 25-ml volumetric flasks, an aliquot of solution containing appropriate amounts of europium, enoxacin, surfactant solution CTMAB and buffer (1.5 ml) were added, and the solution was diluted to the volume with water, shaken and set aside for 30 min at room temperature. The fluorescence intensity was then measured at emission wavelength of 542 nm keeping the excitation wavelength at 275 nm.

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